

OIL AND GAS PROSPECTS OF THE MESO-CENOZOIC FOLDING IN THE "LAND-SEA" TRANSITION ZONE OF THE SOUTH CASPIAN AZERBAIJAN SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

The article, which has been scheduled for publication, focuses on the complex investigation of oil and gas structures and their oil and gas potential in relation to the Meso-Cenozoic sediments along the western coast of the Caspian Sea (South Caspian) in the "land-sea" transition zone. The aim is to prepare recommendations for the justification of exploration and research directions by studying the geological-geophysical status of the research area, analyzing the results of geological interpretation of these studies, the distribution areas of sediments, their lithofacies and structural-tectonic characteristics, as well as analyzing the geodynamic, paleogeographic, and paleotectonic conditions that play a key role in the accumulation and formation of deposits. Additionally, the research examines the oil and gas potential of reservoirs, the litho-physical properties of sediments, and possible migration pathways of hydrocarbons. As a result of the conducted research, several mapping materials have been developed, and based on these materials, the oil and gas potential of the fields and traps has been clarified, and the directions of exploration and research activities have been substantiated.

Keywords: structural, anticlinal, synclinal, tectonically shielded, lithological-stratigraphic, transition zones, well, oil, gas, Mesozoic, Cenozoic, Jurassic, Cretaceous, Eocene, Miocene, Maikop, Diatom, Chokrak, Sarmatian, Quaternary, horizon, roof, bottom, layer thickness.

The western coastal zone of the Caspian Sea within Azerbaijan encompasses the southwestern portion of the Middle Caspian Basin, the northwestern and central areas of the South Caspian Basin, and the Northern Absheron Uplift zone, which separates these basins. The northwestern and central parts of the South Caspian Basin are known for their substantial hydrocarbon potential, with significant global recognition for oil, gas, and condensate reserves.

The Paleogene-Neogene sedimentary complex is extensively distributed throughout Azerbaijan's sector of the Caspian Sea. Most of the discovered hydrocarbon reserves in this region are associated with the sandy horizons of the Lower Pliocene age PS (productive series) within the Neogene system. However, the hydrocarbon potential of the Paleogene sediments remains relatively unexplored due to their deeper burial and generally unsatisfactory lithofacial characteristics in many areas.

To assess the hydrocarbon potential of the Paleogene deposits, it is crucial to examine the oil and gas prospects of the structural-tectonic units located along the western margin of the Caspian Sea and adjacent land areas. In particular, the southeast part of the Middle Caspian Basin, situated within the Terek-Caspian Foredeep, requires detailed analysis. The hydrocarbon potential of Paleogene and Neogene deposits in this foredeep is influenced by the geotectonic development of the sedimentary basins, which affects their lithofacial and structural-tectonic properties (See Fig. 1).

The Terek-Caspian Basin, located between the Epihercin Platform (Turan Platform) and the Greater Caucasus Mountains, features a Paleogene-Neogene sedimentary complex with a thickness of 4-5 km. This complex includes sediments from the Danian, Paleocene, Eocene, Miocene, and Pliocene epochs.

In the southeastern part of the Terek-Caspian Basin, the Paleogene deposits comprise Danian, Paleocene, and Eocene sediments with total thicknesses ranging from 100 to 150 meters. These deposits include fractured limestones interbedded with marl and clay. The Maykop formation is characterized by thick (over 1000 meters) and poorly developed interbedded argillaceous sandstones with gray and dark-gray clays.

The Middle Miocene Tarkhan Horizon consists of claystones interbedded with marl and dolomitized limestones, with thicknesses ranging from 20 to 40 meters. The more substantial Chokrak (300-1100 meters) and Karagan (300-400 meters) horizons are composed of alternating gray sandstones and dark-gray argillaceous siltstones. The thinner Konk Horizon (30-40 meters) consists of sandstones interbedded with marly clays. The thickness of the Lower Pliocene (PS) ranges from 80 to 185 meters and consists of claystones interbedded with gravel, conglomerate, and sandstone layers. Akchagil formation of the Upper Pliocene varies in thickness from 100 to 730 meters and is composed of sandstone and detrital limestone interbedded with claystones.

Fig. 1. Map of Oil-Gas Condensate Structures in the 'Land-Sea' Transition Zone of the Azerbaijan Sector of Caspian Sea

In the western part of the Terek-Caspian Foredeep (Terek-Sunja region) and also in the southeast part (West and East Dagestan anticlines), the Paleogene Danian and Paleocene deposits are not hydrocarbon-rich. Although oil and gas shows were recorded in the Upper Eocene Kum horizon in southern Dagestan, many wells have not tested this horizon. Only in the Selli area of the West Anticline Zone have oil flows of 35-40 tons per day and gas flows of 10-15 thousand cubic meters per day been obtained from the Kum horizon.

The Chokrak and Konk-Karagan horizons are associated with oil fields in the Starıy-Grozny, Dashkala, Oktyabr, and Khoyan-Kort areas of the Sunja Anticlinorium, and with oil and gas fields in most areas of the Terek Anticlinorium. Chokrak sediments also hold significant oil reserves in the Makhachkala, Ternaur, Achi-Su, Izberbash, Inchx-Marine, and Berikay fields in southern Dagestan. However, Konk-Karagan horizons are not hydrocarbon-rich in these areas.

Paleocene, Eocene, and the Khadum horizon deposits have identified some small oil fields in several areas on the platform margin of the Terek-Kum basin. As observed, the hydrocarbon potential in the Paleogene-Neogene deposits of the Terek-Caspian Foredeep is mainly associated with the Middle Eocene and Middle Miocene Chokrak and Konk-Karagan horizons (See Fig. 2).

In northeastern Azerbaijan, within the Yalama-Khudat Uplifts Zone, the Chokrak horizon consists of a variable sequence of claystones, marls, and sandy deposits with thicknesses reaching 350 meters. These deposits differ in thickness from the 260 meters of claystones compared to the sandy deposits. No oil or

gas shows were recorded in the Konk-Karagan horizons while drilling.

In the southwestern part of the Samur-Peschanomysh Uplifts Zone, in the Azerbaijani section of the Yalama-Samur Uplift, drilled YLX-1b well revealed a sharp reduction in the thickness of the Paleogene-Neogene deposits (up to 629 meters) and the primary hydrocarbon-bearing stratigraphic units, the Chokrak and Konk-Karagan horizons, with a significant decrease in thickness (up to 185 meters). Similar to the Yalama-Khudat Uplifts Zone, the lack of oil and gas shows during drilling explains that the prospectivity of these deposits is lower in the anticline crest regions.

In the Zeykhur Depression, which separates the Yalama-Khudat Uplifts Zone from the Qusar-Khachmaz Uplifts Zone, and in the southern-southeastern part of this depression located in the Caspian Sea, there is an increase in the thickness of

Paleogene-Neogene deposits. Drilling in the Agzibirchala Uplift on the Caspian shore has revealed the direct overlap of Pont deposits over the eroded surface of the Middle Jurassic deposits, suggesting the presence of lithostratigraphic and tectonically screened reservoirs in the wing and periclinal parts of these uplift zones. Particularly significant is the southern-southwestern wing of the Qusar-Khachmaz Uplifts Zone opening into the Guba-Davachi depression.

In the Siyazan Monocline located in the southwestern part of the Guba-Davachi depression, oil and gas potential is primarily associated with the Paleogene, especially the Lower Maykop, Eocene, and to a lesser extent, the Dat-Paleocene and Miocene Chokrak horizons.

In the Talabi-Gaynarja Anticline Zone, the Maykop formation, and Middle and Upper Miocene sediments, show the presence of layers with specific resistivities ranging from 2-5 Ohm.m to 20-30 Ohm.m, indicating good permeability. This suggests the potential for high-quality reservoirs in the southern-eastern extension of this anticline zone located in the Caspian Sea area, with the Chokrak horizon displaying significant thickness and potential for hydrocarbon accumulation in the Gızılburun Marine, Zorat-Marine Uplifts, and the southeastern part of the North Absheron Basin (See Fig. 3).

Paleogene-Neogene sediments in the North Absheron Uplifts Zone, including Western Absheron, Northern Absheron, Absheron-Kupesi, Gilevar, and Arzu Uplifts, have been studied through exploration drilling.

The Paleogene-Miocene deposits in the Absheron-Balakhany Anticline Zone in Azerbaijan are not significant in terms of hydrocarbon potential. This is supported by the absence of hydrocarbons in the Eocene sediments with marl and fine-grained sand layers in the Neft Dashlary area and the clay-rich facies of Maykop and Miocene deposits with thicknesses of 120-130 meters and 90-100 meters, respectively.

In contrast to the Middle Caspian Basin, Pliocene sediments in the North Absheron Uplifts Zone exhibit some hydrocarbon potential. Exploration wells in the Northern Absheron, Khazri, Gilevar, Arzu, Dan Ulduzu, Novkhani, Ashrafi, and Karabakh Uplifts have shown that significant industrial oil and gas flows are present only in the northwestern part of the zone, particularly in the Western Absheron and southeastern Ashrafi and Karabakh areas, where Productive Series were encountered.

In the North Absheron Uplifts Zone, the PS deposits in the Absheron-Balakhany Uplifts Zone, separated from the Pirallahi-Kelkor synclinal zone, display high oil and gas saturation. The oil and gas potential of the PS section here covers a broad stratigraphic range from the Gala formation to the Sabunchu formation. Maximum hydrocarbon saturation has been recorded in the Neft Dashlary field. Oil and gas potential in the northern parts of the fields near Neft Dashlary, including Chilov Island, Gurgan-Deniz, Pirallahi Island, and Darwin Kupesi, is restricted to the sand horizons of the lower subunit of Productive Series, including the Gala (GaL), Kirmakialti(KA), and Kirmaki(KL) formations.

In the Bahar field, the V-X horizons of the Balakhani formation, Upper Kirmaki sandstones, and Lower Kirmaki formations are associated with gas-condensate fields, while the Fasila formation is associated with oil fields. In well No.11, gas production from the X horizon reached up to 300 thousand m³/day, with condensate production up to 100 t/day.

In the southern wing of the Absheron Arch, which is separated from the Shahdeniz and Azeri-Chirag-Gunashli(ACG) fields by deep and wide depressions, the ABX-1A well was drilled to a project depth of 6700 meters to study the hydrocarbon potential of the "Fasila" layer sequence. At a depth of 6500 meters, non-industrial gas and water flows were encountered.

The Baku Archipelago, located in the southeastern continuation of the Shamakhi-Gobustan and Lower Kur (neotectonic regional structures), is one of the most promising hydrocarbon regions in the South Caspian Basin. This region's hydrocarbon potential is associated with the upper subunit of PS, particularly the V and VII horizons (analogous to

Fig 3. Map of structures and prospective deposits based on the horizon of the Productive Series and Upper Mesozoic sediments in the 'land-sea' transition zone along the western coast of the Caspian Sea

the "Fasila" layer sequence) and the lower subunit's Upper Kirmaki Sand and Lower Kirmaki formations. The upper part of the PS section, due to the expansion of the water basin, consists of clay deposits from the Paleovolga River's prodelta. These deposits are not expected to be significant for hydrocarbon potential.

In the northern part of the Baku Archipelago, within the "land-sea" transition zone, the main hydrocarbon-bearing targets in the Sangachal-Marine-Khary-Zira Island, Bulla-Marine, and "8 March" fields are the VII and VIII horizons of PS. Except for the "8 March" field, the VIII horizon is being developed for gas-condensate fields. Initial production from wells in the VIII horizon, characterized by high elevations and significant oil saturation, has achieved outputs of 100-200 tons per day of oil, 500-700 thousand cubic meters per day of gas, and 100-130 tons per day of condensate (See Fig. 4).

In the VII horizon, located in the northern wing of the Sangachal-Marine Uplift, there are oil fields with a gas cap, while the northern wing of the Khary-Zira Island Uplift contains oil and gas fields. The V horizon in the northeastern wing of the Khary-Zira Uplift has significant industrial oil and gas potential, although most exploratory wells in the Lower Kirmaki layer have encountered water.

In the buried Bulla-Marine Uplift's northern wing, the V, VII, and VIII horizons of PS hold rich gas-condensate fields. Initial gas production from the V horizon wells ranged from 200-450 thousand cubic meters per day, and condensate production ranged from 70-200 tons per day. Wells producing from the VII horizon achieved gas production of up to 1.8 million

cubic meters per day, with oil and condensate mixed production up to 300 tons per day.

The large-scale Umid-Babek Uplift, located southeast of the Bulla-Marine field, is among the most promising structures in the Baku Archipelago. Although well No. 4 drilled in the northern wing of the Umid Anticline encountered positive hydrocarbon indicators in the VII horizon at a depth of 6715 meters, no test work could be performed. However, well No. 8, drilled closer to the anticline crest, encountered a strong gas fountain at 5910-6000 meters in the VII horizon. The V horizon at this depth also displayed high electrolog characteristics, indicating significant gas-condensate reserves in the Umid and Babek Uplifts.

In the southeastern continuation of the Lower Kura Basin, no significant industrial hydrocarbon fields have been discovered to date. In the northeastern part of the Lower Kura Basin, the Pirsehhet and Hamamdag Uplifts have identified significant oil and gas fields in the VII horizon of PS and in the I, II, and III sand horizons of the Pirsehhet and Lower Pirsehhet formations.

In the Northern Inam Uplift, located along the continuation of the Kurovdag-Neftçala Anticline Zone, well INX-1, with a planned depth of 5000 meters, was abandoned due to geological issues related to anomalous formation pressure at 4700 meters. However, well INX-2, drilled to a depth of 5340 meters, encountered a 10-meter thick oil-saturated section in the X horizon of the Balakhani formation. The hydrocarbon potential of this uplift and other anticlines to the south, such as Inam, Peyk, and Intigam, are associated with sand horizons in the lower part of PS.

Fig 4. Azerbaijan Sector of the Caspian Sea. Map of Oil, Gas, and Condensate Structures and Prospective Structures in the 'Land-Sea' Transition Zone (B.S. Aslanov et al., 2019)

Conventional signs: structures; 1- Oil-rich, 2- Gas-rich, 3- Oil and gas-rich, 4- Condensate-rich, 5- Considered prospective, 6- Breccia observed in mud volcanoes, 7- Tectonic fault lines.

The hydrocarbon potential of the Kurdashi Uplift should be evaluated based on exploration results from the Gizilagac field. Due to the significant clay content in the PS section of the Gizilagac Uplift compared to the Neftçala Uplift, these sediments are less promising for hydrocarbon exploration due to increased clay

content, which affects their prospectivity (See Fig. 3 and 4).

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